

CoreTrustSeal+FAIR: Feedback on Requirements V2.0 (2020-2022)

FAIRsFAIR Project, CoreTrustSeal Board Consultation

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Abstract

This FAIRsFAIR project text is submitted to the CoreTrustSeal Board for comment as part of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements revision process. Suggestions are based on: experience providing support to repositories seeking CoreTrustSeal, object/repository dependencies revealed by aligning the CoreTrustSeal with the FAIR Principles, and the design of CoreTrustSeal+FAIR capability-maturity tiers.

The FAIRsFAIR project has worked with the 2020-2022 (v2.0) of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. In addition to being generally beneficial to the CoreTrustSeal community these suggestions are designed to improve future alignment between CoreTrustSeal and FAIR data. CoreTrustSeal, FAIR and capability-maturity approaches will support repositories seeking to self-assess and plan for prioritisation and improvement, both within and outside the CoreTrustSeal Certification process.

Introduction

This text is the FAIRsFAIR Projects input to the CoreTrustSeal Board for the revision process that will deliver the next version of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements (v3.0 2023-2026).

The feedback and suggestions for the amendment of structure, content and focus are based on the FAIRsFAIR project experience in a number of areas. Proposed amendments include those that would support self-assessment and change prioritisation/management through capability-maturity, and those that would improve alignment with the FAIR Principles.

The project was providing support to 10 repositories seeking CoreTrustSeal certification and considering how CoreTrustSeal may, or may not, apply to a wider range of data services. A number of other object, repository, and service criteria have been reviewed. Work to align the FAIR Data Principles with CoreTrustSeal Requirements that *enable* FAIR Data has been previously shared with the CoreTrustSeal Board. Project work to apply capability-maturity tiers has provided a useful perspective on how some amendments to CoreTrustSeal would help repositories to self-assess, prioritise and move forward in their journey towards enabling FAIR data and becoming trustworthy digital repositories (TDR). We would suggest an overall review of the language used in the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and guidance to maximize alignment with the FAIR Data Principles. The FAIRsFAIR document *FAIR Principles: Baseline Comments*¹ may be a helpful reference for a review of the text.

In addition to being generally beneficial to the CoreTrustSeal community, these suggestions are designed to improve future alignment between CoreTrustSeal and FAIR data as they co-evolve. CoreTrustSeal, FAIR and capability-maturity approaches will support repositories seeking to self-assess and plan for the prioritisation and improvement, both within and outside the CoreTrustSeal Certification process.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472149>

General items of feedback from the supported repositories²:

- Some overall additional clarity would be appreciated by the repositories. It isn't always clear for each requirement what is expected (without asking for help in a support programme).
- There are many relations between the different requirements. This can cause some repetitions to occur throughout the application, as it can be difficult to tell where certain information fits best. It could be helpful to provide more guidance on this, or to make the required answers more clearly distinct.
- More specific processes / information are necessary for different types of repositories. E.g., smaller repositories and institutional repositories found it difficult to follow the CoreTrustSeal certification process and to find suitable guidance.
- The publication of assessments is very valuable for other repositories looking to start the certification process.
 - Some repositories also suggested that the opportunity to directly contact such repositories would be very insightful. Could be a consideration for CoreTrustSeal to ask certified repositories to have their contact details on the website for questions.
- Repositories would have liked more information and/or practical tips on how to work with the application tool. More instructions could be provided to make sure this aspect of the process doesn't take up too much time and effort.
- Permanent financing sources to help keep data alive aren't always available. The mechanisms in the CoreTrustSeal application don't take this into consideration much.
- Reviewer comments could be improved on. Some repositories experienced disparities between reviewers in their feedback. Others found the feedback too vague and would have liked to have more explicit and practical feedback.
- Some repositories expressed a desire or inquiry about why this type of support (FAIRsFAIR support programme) is not provided directly by the CoreTrustSeal themselves. Either through a similar kind of support programme or via the publication of guidance materials and training resources on their website.

² These bullet points reflect recurring or highlighted items from the exit questionnaire and 1:1 interviews conducted with the FAIRsFAIR supported repositories

Diagram: FAIRsFAIR Proposed Alignment Between Principles and Requirements

Rnn. Access

Principles related to data access are vital to F.A.I.R but this function is assumed to be in place by CoreTrustSeal. The primary issue with alignment between the CoreTrustSeal and the FAIR Principles is the lack of a Requirement related to Access. A need to provide access is explicit in R01 Mission but does not have its own requirement, perhaps because the need to provide access to data is seen as obvious and implicit in many requirements.

Not all mappings that seem obvious from the FAIR acronym are valid once the Principles (and associated RDA Working Group indicators) are examined. Whether or not future iterations of CoreTrustSeal+FAIR map access principles to an access requirement we would suggest that clear public statements on how a repository applies its rights framework to digital objects and users during access processes is an important component of a Trustworthy Digital Repository. This is particularly relevant for repositories with more complex access processes such as those holding sensitive data, with non-standard licensing, or conditions of access based on intended data use (project approval) or characteristics of those seeking access (geographic region, training level).

Standards

Standards, in the broadest sense (legislation, licences, best practices, structured (meta)data, file formats) are implied throughout CoreTrustSeal but not explicitly listed anywhere. As registries for these 'standards' evolve they will become easier to reference as supporting information in CoreTrustSeal applications. We would suggest that future iterations of the CoreTrustSeal consider this important information and how it should be presented and connected with self-assessment statements and evidence artefacts provided in CoreTrustSeal applications.

The adherence to standards and best practices could be addressed in the Context section (R0) and standard third-party licences could be included in the Licences (R02), legislation and ethical standards (R4), format lists (R8 and R14), technical standards (R15), security standards (R16) and the delivery of standards compliant (meta)data quality (R11) through workflows (R12). Some community or domain standards are important for the data users of specialist repositories and should be included under ReUse (R14).

Object and Collection Characteristics

Ongoing work to define metrics and tests for data FAIRness will permit repositories and others to evaluate the FAIRness of digital objects. As these metrics and tests become accepted as arbiters of object FAIRness they may also sit alongside other metadata about objects (e.g. associated with their PIDs). Combined with metadata about the repository this will permit sampling of collections or aggregation of FAIRness across a whole collection to provide a FAIR collection 'profile'. We would urge CoreTrustSeal to engage with and monitor these developments with a view to integrating them into future assessments of repositories as FAIR enabling TDRs. The availability of such information may provide a way of streamlining and automating some aspects of certification.

Repository Characteristics

Integrating assessments with repository characteristics as recorded in repository registries. Ongoing work to refine the metadata held about repositories will provide greater depth of information in repository registries. Some aspects of this information may be 'self-declared' by the repository but could still be automatically or manually assessed during a certification process. Other information may be validated by third parties (e.g. other standards or certification bodies). Combined with metadata about the object held by the repository (Object and Collection Characteristics) this will support FAIR collection 'profiles'. One possible example is the association of 'curation and preservation levels' offered by the repository with specific objects. We would urge CoreTrustSeal to engage with and monitor these developments with a view to integrating them into future assessments of repositories as FAIR enabling TDRs. The availability of such information may provide a way of streamlining and automating some aspects of certification.

Compliance and Capability

At present a CoreTrustSeal applicant must indicate a compliance level for each of the Requirements:

- 0 – Not applicable
- 1 – The repository has not considered this yet
- 2 – The repository has a theoretical concept
- 3 – The repository is in the implementation phase
- 4 – The guideline has been fully implemented in the repository

The FAIRsFAIR capability/maturity approach could partially replace these levels with the application and review process focussing instead on whether a requirement has been fully implemented or whether the repository is in the implementation phase. If the latter is the case the applicant would describe plans and timescales for implementation (as is currently the case for CoreTrustSeal).

Ideally this approach would be adopted and managed by the CoreTrustSeal and included either in their 'extended guidance' document or as a separate capability-maturity self-assessment text. The use of the capability tiers would provide guidance during initial self-assessments and support

repository planning for improvement. We would suggest that the final application for CoreTrustSeal continues to focus on prose self-assessment statements with links to public evidence. If capability-maturity levels are included in an application this should be for informational purposes only, the 'core' nature of CoreTrustSeal and its periodic nature (snapshots of repository status every three years) mean that it is not a process suited to peer-review of granular capability-maturity levels.

The current CoreTrustSeal compliance levels that support self-assessments and applications use a mixed scale approach that covers applicability, awareness and implementation levels. Suggested practice here is discussed in the FAIRsFAIR Capability-Maturity Design Statement. We provide a suggested capability-maturity approach in a separate text, but would suggest that whether or not this is adopted the future CoreTrustSeal should separate out:

-*applicability*- with 'not applicable' supported by an explanation';

-*implementation*- with in progress achievements accompanied by information about what is planned and any timing or event triggers e.g. our persistent identifier system implementation is in progress and will be delivered by [date].

Support

Support (particularly at the points of deposit and reuse) might be implied but is not explicit in the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. Would the clarification of support provided to depositors and end users be a useful addition to CoreTrustSeal?

Requirement-Specific Feedback

Blank entries have no related feedback or suggestions.

R0. Context

Repository Type

Level of Curation Performed

Insource/Outsource Partners

Organisational Infrastructure

R01. Mission (Rights)

R02. Licences (Rights)

The current title may cause an assumption that licences are always formal 'documents' that are 'signed' between two parties. An entirely open repository with no conditions for deposit or access may assume this does not apply to them. We would recommend this requirement is changed to 'rights management' so that the need to have clear permissions, prohibitions and duties in place is clear. This should be an assurance that all relevant issues are covered for data and metadata whether deposited, created/enriched by the repository, and include the right to take actions to preserve data and metadata. This coverage should be distinct from R04 below to avoid overlap.

This is a challenging area and one that will require considerable future investment if rights statements are to become generally machine-readable and machine actionable (e.g. through Open Digital Rights Language- ODRL expressions).

R03. Continuity of Access

Some applicants may be confused by the focus on ‘access’ here. Partially because ‘continued access’ is partially assured through preservation (R10) but also because basic access to digital objects in the face of adversity is not sufficient to meet the requirement. Overall ‘service continuity’ including disaster recovery is required.

Succession planning should similarly go beyond a handover of digital objects to assure future storage or basic access and consider what level of current service function can be maintained (or lost) if a succession plan is implemented. As noted in FAIRsFAIR outputs³ succession planning is a very high bar for many repositories and local circumstances may prevent a formal plan. The CoreTrustSeal approach to continuity should take this into consideration but the level of succession planning in place should still be as transparent as possible.

R04. Confidentiality/Ethics (Legal & Ethical)

This requirement mentions legal environments, but focuses heavily on evidence related to sensitive data. The provision of information about legislation and ethical policies (at the international, national, regional and domain/disciplinary levels) is a clear candidate for a shared ‘registry’ that would greatly reduce repository investment and overall risk to digital objects and data services. We would suggest that this requirement be amended to include ‘legal’ in the title. As not all repositories handle sensitive (personal, cultural, commercial) data we would also ask whether CoreTrustSeal would consider separating these elements of the requirement into a subsection, or even differentiating certifications for those handling such data.

R05. Organisational Infrastructure

Apart from the fact that this Requirement title repeats the overall heading for Requirements R01 to R06 it might be made clearer by referring specifically to the organisational management, including of resources. References to ‘qualified’ staff might imply an overlap with R06 ‘expert guidance’ (which references both internal and external expertise); this separation could be more clearly defined.

R06. Expert Guidance

As noted above, it might be more clear to applicants if R05 focussed on governance and resources with R06 reserved for qualifications, knowledge and skills. It could be made clear that this requirement covers two key areas: 1. that the expertise needed is understood and is either delivered internally or sought externally and 2. that the repository engages with the wider community in relevant areas of practice.

The FAIRsFAIR CapMat model proposes an additional evaluation of community engagement for R06. If the CoreTrustSeal sees value in a separate assessment of engagement then we would suggest the Requirement title reflects this e.g. Expertise and Engagement.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5346822>

Digital Object Management

R07. Integrity and Authenticity

Though integrity (avoiding unintended change) and authenticity (managing and recording intended change) are 'two sides of the same coin' their implementation is distinct. In providing support for CoreTrustSeal applicants we have noted an imbalance in responses to this Requirement. The more curation focussed self-assessors have issues with integrity measures while the more technical tend to focus on integrity to the exclusion of authenticity evidence. This may also reflect a lack of community agreed minima on what authenticity information (Provenance, cf: PROV⁴ approach to entities, agents and activities) should be provided for different levels of curation and different use cases.

For this reason we suggest that this requirement should also use the term 'provenance' and consider whether storage integrity would be better placed under Technology.

R08. Appraisal

This requirement could either be specifically focussed on the deposit stage, or widened to be clearer about the need for reappraisal of data and metadata over time. Otherwise reappraisal could be covered under R10. Preservation Plan

R09. Storage

As for 'integrity' in R07, even though the focus of R07 to R14 is on curation for digital object management in our support activities the responses tend to focus on the technical aspects of storage with a large overlap between statements for R09 and integrity aspects of R07. In our capability-maturity draft we provide proposed capability-maturity tiers for storage, but would suggest that R09 should be combined with 'integrity' and added to the Technology section.

R10. Preservation Plan

R11. Quality

Quality is a broad and hard to define concept and R11 presents some challenges to applicants as it stands. The reference to 'appropriate expertise' may already have been addressed through R05 and R06. There is a reference to providing 'sufficient information to end users' to make decisions about 'quality' that seems to relate to fitness for purpose (e.g. scientific quality), but this might sit more logically under ReUse (R14). Otherwise the focus is on technical quality control in terms of 'standards compliance' and evidence sought includes information about the 'approach' that seems to rapidly overlap with 'workflows'. This is understandable as quality assurance and control for standards compliance depend on workflows.

We suggest that these two requirements could, if combined, map closely to the curation phase of the repository work ('ingest' in OAIS terms) including providing the foundation for preservation actions. Reference to some standard approach to quality descriptions might also support applicants e.g.

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

Bruce & Hillman (2004⁵) refer to completeness, accuracy, provenance, conformance to expectations, logical consistency and coherence and timeliness (currency and lag).

Ultimately workflows that ensure standards compliance are intended to ensure that (meta)data is curated so that it can be preserved (R10) and reused (R14).

R12. Workflows (Standards, Quality & Workflows)

There are two additional arguments for aligning standards and workflows

1. There does not seem to be any disagreement that documented/diagrammed workflows, business processes, standard operating procedures etc are desirable and necessary. But there is a lack of public repository (and wider data service) workflow examples and no community agreed minimum expectations.
2. The recognition that shared common registries of supporting information are necessary to support consolidated research infrastructure would suggest that it will become easier to share and refer to community standards and workflows over time. In an ideal scenario it should be simple for metadata in a repository registry to link to standards that a repository claims to comply with.

R13. Discovery & Identification

As no 'approved' list of providers exists, it may not be appropriate for CoreTrustSeal to reject an applicant that provided evidence for an effective local system acceptable to their designated community. But the CoreTrustSeal could specify expectations that persistent identifiers (PID) be managed, follow a defined syntax, and are globally unique and resolvable. The CoreTrustSeal could also reference the EOSC PID Policy⁶.

R14. ReUse

The ReUse Requirement of CoreTrustSeal assesses two broad areas:

1. The means by which the repository identifies and addresses the needs of the designated community.
2. The characteristics of the data and metadata in the digital objects that meet these needs.

Some of these characteristics might be candidates for recording as object metadata (e.g. alongside the registration of a PID in DataCite metadata). Others are dependent on the standards, schemas and formats selected to ensure that the data meets the needs of the designated community.

This requirement is distinct from R10 Preservation, but many of the actions needed to respond to change and make digital objects reusable 'now' are the same actions that need long term planning as part of R10. The characteristics necessary for ReUse are either present at Appraisal (R08) or curated for at Quality (R11). Careful separation of expectations would reduce duplication and facilitate a clearer capability-maturity approach.

⁵ [The Continuum of Metadata Quality: Defining, Expressing, Exploiting](#)

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/ki0420576enn-updt.pdf

Technology

R15. Technical Infrastructure

R16. Security